

Natural Resource Rents and CO₂ Emissions in West Africa: The Institutional Quality Dilemma?

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Abstract

Natural resource exploitation can fuel economic growth by generating resource rents, but this growth comes at a cost: significant environmental degradation. As resource rents rise, so do carbon emissions and environmental degradation, highlighting the need for sustainable management of natural resources to balance economic benefits with environmental protection. Consequently, this study examines how natural resource rents impact environmental quality, and whether regulatory quality can mitigate any adverse effects. Specifically, it investigates the relationship between resource rents, environmental quality, and regulatory quality from 1990 to 2022. The study utilized unbalanced panel dataset of fifteen (15) West African countries. For techniques, the study used the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimator in addition to panel unit root and cointegration. The study used Kao and Westerlund cointegration procedures found co-movement among the variables. The PMG empirical result asserted that the environment further degrades as resource rents increases. The PMG also divulged that institutional quality exacerbate the environmental damaging effect of resource rents. Thus, reducing the level of CO₂ emissions and improving the environment will require policy makers and government of the African countries to lower their dependence on the extractive sector, the extraction and utilization of mineral resources and exploring other energy source through scaling up research and investment in hydropower, solar, wind and geothermal energy sources.

Keywords: Natural resource rents, CO₂ emissions, institutional quality, EKC and PMG

JEL Classifications: O₁₃, Q₅₄, E₀₂, and C₂₃,

i. Introduction

Interestingly, just as a specific range of temperatures supports sustainable life and environmental quality on Earth, even slight deviations can have far-reaching and potentially devastating consequences for sustainable life and environmental quality. An increase in the level of greenhouse gas (GHGs) emissions above a certain threshold can tip the scale and push temperatures beyond a critical limit, leading to severe consequences. According to the Inter-Governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in its 2020 Special Report on Global Warming, a global temperature above 1.5⁰C could have catastrophic impact on economic activities, health, food security, among others, and an increase in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions above 330 billion tons could cause global temperature to rise above 1.5⁰C and birth far-reaching consequences such as prevalence of diseases, drought, floods, food insecurity, and decline in economic activities, among other cascading effects of climate change. In recent years, human activities have led to a surge in greenhouse gas emissions, particularly carbon dioxide, which is driving global warming and climate change. Arguably, carbon dioxide emissions remain the leading cause of global warming and contributor to climate change. Which has fueled the global campaign to reduce CO₂ emissions in order to preserve and sustain the environment [6]. The concerted effort to rescue and preserve the environment from further degradation requires the identification of the factor(s) responsible for increment in CO₂ emissions and those that abate growth of CO₂ emissions.

Research suggests that economic growth is a key driver of increased carbon dioxide emissions, with expanding economic activities often resulting in higher emissions. This link is conceptualized by the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) which, suggests that economic growth is responsible for environmental degradation and has an inverted U-shaped relationship with CO₂ emissions. As suggested by the theory, environment pollution is pronounced in the early developmental stage as the country strives to be industrialized, it peaks and declines as income becomes optimized following the deployment of technological advancements in the production process; and the ability to efficiently use

energy to produce larger quantities of output [30] and [32]. Evidence from empirical studies have shown that economic growth is among the leading contributors to environmental pollution and validates the EKC hypothesis [15]; [16]; [35]; [36]; [37] and [38].

While economic growth is often linked to environmental pollution, some research suggests that natural resource rents play a significant role in driving carbon dioxide emissions. The exploration of natural resource has been a catalyst for economic growth in developing countries, including those in the West African region. The strong economic growth experienced in Nigeria, Ghana, Guinea, Mali, Senegal, among other West African countries in the 2000s could be partly attributed to exports of natural resources, including other reforms and a semblance of political stability (World Bank, 2020; [5] Though the exploration, exploitation and subsequent export of these natural resources, which lay in vast quantities under the earth crust of countries in the West African region, have provided enormous rents that has supported government expenditure, the continuous exploitation poses severe environmental risks that threaten the region's sustainability goals. The exploration and exploitation of natural resources most often leads to land and air pollution, emitting carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases, which degrades the environment and threatens economic growth, food security, and sustainable livelihoods, among other effects ([5]; [4]). In Nigeria, particularly the Niger Delta region, the extraction of crude oil has been linked to the disruption of aquatic lives, economic and social livelihoods of residents in the region. The inappropriate exploitation of these resources, lax environmental regulations and use of obsolete technology has contributed to the increased CO₂ emissions, degrading the environment. According to [26], the exploration of natural resources is intensive at the early stage of economic growth, causing an uptick in pollution emissions. This is attributed to the premium placed on achieving rapid economic growth over environmental performance. There are empirical studies that have discussed the relationship between natural resource rents and carbon emissions and establish that natural resource rents increase the amount of carbon emissions ([5]; [6]; [11]; [14]; [15]; [20]; [34]).

Natural resource rent can be defined as difference between the revenue derived from the extraction of the resource and the cost of extraction. Natural resource exploitation, though economically beneficial, significantly contributes to rising carbon emission. Notably, the empirical evidence by [14] and [34], and others demonstrate that natural resource rents worsen environmental conditions. Contrasting views on the factors that influence carbon emissions suggests that the quality of institutions matters in the relationship between natural resource rents and carbon emission, positing that the negative disruption of natural resource rents on the environment can be mitigated in an environment with high institutional quality ([9] and [34]). The idea behind this is that strong institutions can mitigate the harmful effect of natural resource rents on the environment through policies such as carbon taxing, elimination of subsidies on fossil fuels. Institutional quality can also moderate the relationship between natural resource rents and carbon emissions by influencing and improving energy efficiency [16]. Institutions and their quality also matter in reducing the level of carbon emissions. Countries with strong institutions (characterized by efficient public service, regulatory control, minimal bureaucracy) can boost the confidence of investors and effectively design and enforce governmental rules and regulations geared toward curbing carbon emissions. By extension, weak institutions could escalate carbon emissions as ineffective regulations could constrain efforts by government to reduce carbon emissions [1]; [21].

Based on the foregoing, the role of institutions and their quality is indispensable in reducing the emission levels from natural resource rents. In view of this, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse by re-evaluating the environmental implications of natural resource rent across West Africa. The study tries to answer certain pertinent questions: 1) Does increasing earnings from the exploration and exploitation of natural resources elevate the level of carbon emissions in the West African countries? 2) Does strong institutions or regulatory control mitigate the environmental degradation feared from the increased natural resource rents? This study also builds on existing research by investigating both linear and nonlinear links between natural resource rents and environmental degradation, using the Pooled Mean Group method to re-examine the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis.

The rest of paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews existing literature, Section 3 outlines the data and methodology, Section 4 presents the empirical findings, and Section 5 concludes with policy recommendations

ii. Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

At the theoretical level, the relationship between natural resource rent and CO₂ emissions is understood from two main literature: the environmental Kuznets curve proposed by Kuznets (1956) and the treadmill production theory credited to Schnaiberg (1970). The EKC hypothesis remains the widely used hypothesis that describes the relationship between environmental quality and economic growth [38]. According to [31] the EKC hypothesis allude to a nonlinear

long-run relationship between economic growth and environmental pollution/degradation. The hypothesis, first popularized by Kuznets, argues that there is an inverted U-shaped relationship between economic growth and environmental quality, suggesting that economic growth increases CO₂ emissions in the early stage of economic development which reduces the quality of the environment, and only improving the performance of the environment once a saturated level of income is reached or the country achieves a certain level of national income ([27]; [33]). Stated differently, the hypothesis argues that CO₂ emissions increases with improvement in per capita income in the early stage of economic development resulting from industrialization, then at a later stage, CO₂ emissions peaks and begins to decline as further per capita income growth improves environmental performance. According to [33] the decline in CO₂ emissions experienced in the later stage of economic development can be attributed to energy-efficiency and the use of sophisticated technology which occurs during this stage of development coupled with strong and stringent legislation and enforcement, producing a decline in CO₂ emissions and improvement in the conditions of the environment.

The increase in CO₂ emissions which have harmful impacts on the environment as rents from the exploitation and exploration of natural resource trend in the positive direction have been explained by the treadmill production theory. The theory proposed by Schnaiberg (1970) provides the connecting link between economic growth and environmental pollution. Basically, the theory argues that one of the factors responsible or that drives the poor performance of the environment is the yearning by economic agents for a prosperous life [6] The position of this theory is that the desire for rapid economic growth and development, propels a huge quest for new technologies and natural resources. The idea behind the theory is that the pursuit of higher levels of economic growth and development by economic agents exerts enormous pressure on energy demand, inducing fresh investments in the exploitation of natural resources. Though the exploitation of natural resources results in an uptrend movement in the contribution of the extractive or mining sector to overall output, which facilitate aggregate output expansion, the quality of environment declines on account on enormous pressure on the environment derived from upscale in the extraction of natural resources ([5] and [6]).

Empirical Literature

Reference [24] concerned with the environmental problem of carbon emission, questioned whether the implementation of anti-corruption policies by government will improve the quality of the environment. They examined the validity of the environmental Kuznets' curve (EKC) hypothesis for 158 countries from 2002 to 2018 and experiment whether economic growth nonlinearly affect ecological footprint. Using natural resource rents and corruption control as threshold variables, their panel threshold regression results show that the negative effect of economic growth on the environment is more pronounced in a low-quality institutional environment. [14] used the method of moment quantile regression to examine the factors that contribute to environmental pollution and/or abate CO₂ emissions for 5 BRICS countries from 1990 to 2019. Their estimation outcome which was robust to the use of the augmented mean group (AMG) and common correlated effect mean group (CCEMG) revealed that government expenditure, natural resource rents, and economic growth increases CO₂ emissions, whereas renewable energy consumption abate carbon emissions.

[19] explored the determinants of carbon emissions in United States of America from 1971 to 2016 and reported through the generalized method of moments (GMM) that increased natural resource rents and population growth have detrimental effects on the environment. Furthermore, they observed that renewable energy consumption has carbon emissions abating influence. [28] revisited the EKC hypothesis, assessing the role of foreign direct investment in carbon emissions for 20 Latin America countries from 1990 to 2018. Employing the dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) method and Dumitrescu and Hurlin approach to causality, they found that Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) contribute to carbon emissions, with CO₂ emissions increasing by 0.05% as FDI inflows rises by 1%. [30] employing the panel dynamic and fully modified OLS methods find an N-shaped relationship between income growth and CO₂ emissions in the BRICS countries. Studying these countries from 1992 to 2014, they also found evidence supporting the haven hypothesis as FDI contributes to carbon emissions. [10] studied the BRICS countries from 1992 to 2017 exploring the factors that worsen or abate pollution using the fixed effect method. Their results show that there is an inverted U-shaped relationship between income and pollution, validating the EKC hypothesis, Also, they demonstrated that energy consumption contributes to pollution. In a study of 76 developing and developed countries from 2002 to 2012, [3] using the fixed effect method and robust by the generalized method of moments find the effect of FDI on the environment depends on the source of FDI inflows. They noted that FDI coming from developing countries worsen the environmental conditions of lower- and lower-middle-income (LLMI) countries, also FDI inflows from developed countries reduces pollution in LLMI countries. [32] investigated the sources of carbon emissions in six GCC countries from 1993 to 2019. The mean group, augmented mean group and common correlated effect mean group results demonstrate that financial deepening significantly makes the environment of the Gulf countries clean and less polluted. Further results disclose that natural resource rents, nonrenewable energy consumption and economic growth have environmental degrading influence.

[5] examined if strong institutions and regulatory frameworks (regulatory control) can mitigate the environmental damage caused by natural resource rents in 41 sub-Saharan African countries. He split the countries into 21 non-resource dependent countries (NRDCs) and 20 resource-dependent countries (RDCs). The cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (CS-ARDL) results showed that while natural resource rent has environmental degrading effect, strong regulatory environment reduces the pollution caused by increased earnings from natural resource exploitation. [15] in a study of G7 countries using the dynamic OLS, fully modified OLS, augmented mean group, and quantile regression techniques find that higher income level and increase earnings from exploration and exploitation of natural resources fuel degeneration of the environment. Inference from the estimation identified renewable energy consumption as reducing CO₂ emissions for the G7 countries. [33] investigated the implication of natural resource rents and institutional quality on CO₂ emissions in 42 SSA countries studied from 1994 to 2020. The two-step system generalized method of moments (SGMM) results indicated that natural resource rents, trade openness and institutional quality drive up CO₂ emissions, while carbon emissions in the region declines with increased foreign direct investment, confirming that the halo effect hypothesis holds in the region. [7] used the structural vector autoregressive (SVAR) model to analyse quarterly data from 1990Q1 – 2018Q4 to assess the environmental effect of natural resource rents, hydropower consumption, and urban population. They reported that hydropower consumption, urbanization and economic growth mitigate carbon emissions. Their results confirmed that natural resource rent have deteriorating impact on the environment in Sudan.

[6] employed the fixed effect, random effect, augmented mean group and feasible generalized least square to investigate whether natural resource rent and globalization are potential inducers of carbon emissions in 5 rich African countries. The author document that mineral, crude oil and nature gas rents, and globalization significant degrade the environment. [11] researched the impact of natural resource rents on environmental sustainability in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) countries. The estimation of the data from 2003 – 2020 was based on the panel quantile regression with fixed effects and they demonstrated that economic growth and earnings from oil and mineral resources increase carbon emissions. Further results revealed that forest resource rent mitigate emissions for the MENA countries. While studying 20 Latin American countries from 1990 to 2018, [28] confirmed using the dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) method that foreign direct investment substantially aggravates carbon emissions, with the impact more severe in the sample of high-income countries compared to the upper-middle- and lower-middle income countries. [13] analysed the linkage between foreign direct investment and CO₂ emissions for 12 Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) countries from 1995 – 2014. They demonstrated that foreign direct investment initially has detrimental effect on the environment, but improves the quality of the environment after a certain threshold level. In addition, their result revealed that energy consumption contributes to pollution and the initial environmental degrading effect of foreign direct investment diminishes when FDI reaches a certain threshold.

[2] used the cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (CS-ARDL) method to demonstrate that imports and financial development worsen the environmental problems in the MINT countries. Their analysis revealed that exports and renewable energy consumption do improve the environmental conditions in countries studied. [20] who employed the cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (CS-ARDL) method to assess the determinants of consumption-based CO₂ emissions in the G7 countries from 1990 – 2017 found that exports, renewable energy consumption and environmental innovation substantially abate consumption-related CO₂ emissions. They noted that imports and industrial value added contributes to environmental degradation. [25] used the panel quantile regression method to assess the nexus between urbanization, international trade and CO₂ emissions of 65 Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) countries from 2000 to 2016. Employing the 2-stages least square method, they demonstrated that the EKC hypothesis is valid and there is an inverted U-shaped relationship between urbanization and CO₂ emissions. As demonstrated, CO₂ emissions in the countries studied increases with increase in energy consumption, foreign direct investment and population. [34] adopted the cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (CS-ARDL) method to analyse data of 7 Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) from 1990 to 2018. They confirmed that natural resource rent adversely affects the environment, while strong institutions contribute to environmental improvement.

iii. Data and Methodology

Nature and Sources of Data

This study analyses unbalanced annual panel data from 1990 to 2022 for 15 West African countries. The following countries were chosen based on data availability: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cote d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, and Togo. This study uses CO₂ emissions in million metric tonnes (mt) as a measure of CO₂ emissions, and natural resource rents in terms of GDP is the proxy for natural resource rents. Real gross domestic product per capita is used to measure economic growth, the

composite financial development index is used as proxy of financial development to capture the multidimensional nature of financial development, net foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows as proportion of GDP is employed as FDI measure, and electricity production is measured using total electricity production in billion kilowatt-hours (kWh). Urbanization is proxy by growth in urban population, the sum of aggregate exports and imports as proportion of GDP is used to measure trade openness, and regulatory framework is used proxy of institutional quality. Four data sources were use in extracting data for the series, namely, the World Bank's World Development Indicator (WDI), the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), the World Governance Indicator (WGI), the Global Carbon Map database, and the International Energy Agency (EIA). The data for real GDP per capita, FDI, were sourced from UNCTAD, whereas data on urbanization, trade openness, and natural resource rents are obtained from WDI. Electricity production and institutional quality data were sourced from EIA and WGI database, respectively. Data on CO₂ emissions were extracted from the Global Carbon Map database.

Empirical Model

To analyse the effect of natural resource rent on CO₂ emissions for 15 West African countries, this study estimates a functional model derived from the augmented Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis which is close to the model used by Afolabi (2023).

The baseline model is expressed as:

$$\lnco2_{it} = \delta_0 + \theta_1 \lnco2_{i,t-1} + \theta_2 nr_{it} + \theta_3 \lneg_{it} + \theta_4 fd_{it} + \theta_5 fdi_{it} + \theta_6 \lnepd_{it} + \theta_7 urb_{it} + \theta_8 ton_{it} + \vartheta_i + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where, $CO2_{it}$ is carbon emissions; nr_{it} is the variable of interest which is natural resource rent; eg_{it} represent economic growth; fd_{it} is financial development; fdi_{it} represent foreign direct investment; epd_{it} is electricity production; urb_{it} stands for urbanization; ton_{it} is trade openness; ϑ_i represent time-invariant cross-sectional units specific effect; γ_t represent time dummies; ε_{it} is well-behaved error term; $\theta_1 - \theta_8$ are coefficients to be estimated; subscript i represent cross-section and subscript t denotes time index.

The study examined if strong regulatory environments can mitigate the negative impact of natural resource rents on the environment, focusing on the moderating role of regulatory control in the interaction between natural resource rent and CO₂ emission. To achieve this, the study remodelled Eqn. (1) to capture this conditional effect and this was done by including the product of natural resource rent and institutional proxy, that is ($nr_{it} \times inq_{it}$), into Eqn. (1).

The extended Eqn. (1) becomes:

$$\lnco2_{it} = \delta_0 + \theta_1 \lnco2_{i,t-1} + \theta_2 nr_{it} + \theta_3 inq_{it} + \theta_4 (nr_{it} * inq_{it}) + \theta_5 \lneg_{it} + \theta_6 fd_{it} + \theta_7 fdi_{it} + \theta_8 \lnepd_{it} + \theta_9 urb_{it} + \theta_{10} ton_{it} + \vartheta_i + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Here inq_{it} is institutional quality which is measured using regulatory control, $nr_{it} * inq_{it}$ represent the interactive term; and other notations remain as defined.

The marginal effect of natural resource rent on CO₂ emissions is obtained by taking the partial derivative of Eqn. (2) with respect to NR and this give:

$$\frac{\partial \lnco2_{it}}{\partial nr_{it}} = \theta_2 + \theta_4 inq_{it} \quad (3)$$

Eqn. (3) indicates the role of institutional quality in moderating the effect of natural resource rent on CO₂ emissions, and this is interpreted based on the sign, magnitude and significance of θ_2 and θ_4 . Four possible outcomes could emerge and be interpreted as: If $\theta_2 > 0$ and $\theta_4 < 0$, it suggests that natural resource rent reduces environmental quality, but a strong institutional environment reduces the negative effect of resource rent on the environment. Second, if $\theta_2 > 0$ and $\theta_4 > 0$, natural resource rent has negative influence on the environment and strong institutions complement natural resource rent in degrading the environment. Third, if $\theta_2 < 0$ and $\theta_4 > 0$, it suggests that an environment with strong institutions will reduce the harmful effect of natural resource rent on the environment. Fourth, if $\theta_2 < 0$ and $\theta_4 < 0$, it means that natural resource rent and institutions have substitutionary effect in improving the environment.

Slope homogeneity (SH)

Another challenge in panel analysis is the potential of heterogeneity of the slope coefficients. This is because each cross-section may have differences in terms of pace of economic prosperity and development, financial development, culture, and environmental policies, among others. Thus, controlling for heterogeneity becomes essential, as not accounting for it may result in unreliable estimation outcome. To address this problem, the study employed the method proposed by [22] in investigating slope homogeneity. The assumption of the null hypothesis is that the regression coefficients are homogenous and this is tested against the alternative hypothesis which assumes heterogeneity of the slopes.

Cross-sectional dependence (CSD)

In panel data analysis, it is possible that the cross-sectional units might depend on each other. The source of such possible dependency comes from increased integration of economies on the back of globalization, regional trade agreements to bolster intra-trade among regional countries, financial globalization. There is the possibility that these linkages can funnel shocks from one country to another in the panel and it is essential that this problem be considered when conducting panel analysis, as the results obtained from the estimated model would be biased and inconsistent. Furthermore, the assumption of an independent cross-sectional units could cause misleading inferences to emerge between the considered predictor variables and outcome variable. Thus, the detection of CSD becomes crucial in panel analysis, with its resolution necessary before checking for the stationarity properties of pivotal variables. In testing for the presence of CD, the CD test developed by [29] is applied. The null hypothesis of [29] CD test suggests independence, tested against the alternative hypothesis which suggests dependence. Rejecting the null hypothesis would mean that shock in one of the cross-sectional units is transmitted to other units in the panel.

The CD test is based off a test statistic and this is computed using the equation below:

$$CD_{stat} = \sqrt{\frac{2t}{n(n-1)} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \widehat{\rho}_{ij} \right)} \quad (4)$$

ρ represent pairwise correlation.

Panel Unit Root Test

It is important that an appropriate unit root approach is applied in determining the stationarity properties of the pivotal variables. Identifying the integration process of each selected variables is important to avoid a spurious regression, an associated problem with estimating variables that are unstable. Two types of panel unit root tests exist when dealing with panel data series – there is the first- and second-generation unit root approaches. The application of either depends on the results of the CSD test. In the presence of interrelationship among the cross-sectional units, first-generation panel unit root approaches cannot be used to check for stability of the series due to its rejection of the null hypothesis which suggests presence of unit root. The second-generation unit root approaches are applied upon rejecting the null hypothesis of the CSD test. With results suggesting that CSD does not exist, the first-generation unit root testing approaches were applied. The study adopted the [23] and [31] approaches in determining the order of integration of the series used.

The LLC (2002) statistics is computed using the equation below:

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \varphi_i + \alpha Y_{i,t-1} + \sum_{r=1}^m \alpha_{ir} \Delta Y_{i,t-r} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

Here: Y_{it} denote the considered variables which are $lnco2_{it}$, nr_{it} , $lneg_{it}$, fd_{it} , fdi_{it} , $lnepd_{it}$, urb_{it} , ton_{it} , and inq_{it} ; Δ is the first difference operator; and ln represent logarithmic transformation. The null hypothesis is that: $H_0: \delta = 0$ and tested against the alternative which assumes that: $H_1: \delta < 0$, denoting stable series.

For the IPS (2003) test, the specification for computing the statistics is written as follows:

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \vartheta_i + \alpha_i Y_{i,t-1} + \sum_{r=1}^m \alpha_{ir} \Delta Y_{i,t-r} + \theta_i t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (6)$$

The null hypothesis assumes $H_0: \alpha_i = 0$ for all cross-sectional units. The alternative hypothesis holds that $H_1: \alpha_i < 0$ for atleast one cross-section.

Panel Cointegration Test

If there exists non-stationary variable(s) among the sets of considered variables in the model used to understand the factors that drive or abate the emissions of carbon in the West African countries, then a test of cointegration to determine if the combined pivotal variables have common trend in the long run is crucial. This is to ensure that estimation outcomes are trustworthy and not spurious, as it is the case for nonstationary series whose response to shocks are not transitory, but rather permanent. To illuminate if there is co-movement among considered series, cointegrating testing is done. However, the approach to this test hinges on the outcome of the CSD test. If the assumption of dependency among cross-sectional units exist, cointegration approach like Kao test will generate bias and unreliable coefficients. In this study, the cointegration test introduced by [18] and [37] were used to investigate cointegration of the considered variables, as the methods assumes cross-sectional independence.

The Westerlund equation for obtaining the test statistics is written as:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \vartheta'_i d_t + \theta_i (y_{i,t-1} - \alpha'_i x_{i,t-1}) + \sum_{r=1}^t \beta_{ir} \Delta y_{i,t-r} + \sum_{r=1}^t \pi_{im} \Delta x_{i,t-r} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (7)$$

Where θ_i is the error correction estimate, Δ represent first difference operator, y_{it} is carbon emission variable and x_{it} is k dimensional regressors.

Analytical technique

The method adopted in analysing the dataset of the cross-sections is the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimator, proposed by [The PMG method is better than the fixed effect, random effect, and generalized method of moments (GMM) estimators in a number of ways: the method addresses the endogeneity issue that occurs from the inclusion of the lagged dependent variable as regressor; it provides long- and short-run estimates for the relationship between the regressors and CO₂ emissions; and the method considers heterogeneous slopes in the short and assume common coefficients in the long run [8].

The specification of the panel PMG model for Eqn. (1) and (2) is written as:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \delta_i + \theta_i (y_{i,t-1} - \lambda'_i x_{i,t-1}) + \sum_{r=1}^{m-1} \psi_{ir} \Delta y_{i,t-r} + \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \vartheta_{ir} \Delta x_{i,t-r} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (8)$$

Here y_{it} is CO₂ emissions; x_{it} represent vector of pivotal regressors; λ'_i is the long-run equilibrium between CO₂ emissions and vector of regressors; θ_i represent the error correction term; ψ_{ir} and ϑ_{ir} are short run coefficients to be estimated; and items in the parentheses reflect long-run relationship between CO₂ emissions and vector of regressors.

iv. Findings and discussion

Table 1: Result of Descriptive Analysis

	CO ₂	NR	EG	FD	FDI	EPD	URB	TON	INQ
Mean	9.068	10.364	1027.638	0.109	2.827	2.951	3.950	58.670	-0.609
Max	131.113	59.433	3689	0.292	32.300	32.787	7.886	131.485	0.268
Min	0.146	1.716	141	0.022	-2.880	0.019	-1.065	16.352	-1.570
S.D	24.299	7.935	674.702	0.047	3.741	6.050	1.050	19.018	0.359
Skw.	3.701	2.082	1.572	1.165	3.050	3.017	0.042	0.767	-0.188
Kurt.	15.582	10.121	5.354	4.575	17.184	12.318	5.259	3.488	2.467
J.B.	4395.83	1361.468	318.317	158.317	4897.621	2465.191	105.438	53.131	7.434
Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.024
Obs.	495	480	495	480	493	480	495	492	420

Note: CO₂ is carbon emission; NR = natural resource rents; EG = per capita GDP; FD = financial development; FDI = foreign direct investment; EPD = electricity production; URB = urbanization; TON = trade openness; INQ = institutional quality
Source: As compiled by Authors (2025)

Before estimating the panel model to check the effect of natural resource rent on CO₂ emissions, the study examined the descriptive properties of the employed variables. Table 1 presents the summary statistics for carbon dioxide emissions, natural resource rents, economic growth, financial development, foreign direct investment, electricity production, urbanization, trade openness, and institutional quality. According to the summary statistics, an average of 9.068 million metric tonnes (mt) of CO₂ is emitted into the atmosphere by the countries studied and the volume of CO₂ emissions rose within the period to 131.113 million metric tonnes (mt) from 0.146 million metric tonnes. In proportion to gross domestic product, earnings from natural resource exploration by the West African countries averaged 10.364%. Between 1990 and 2022, earnings realized from natural resource exploration inched from 1.716 to 59.433% in proportion to GDP. This result shows the degree to which the economy of the West African countries depends on activities in the extractive sector. Economic growth in the region remains slow and moderate, shown by GDP per capita which averaged USD 1,027.638. Income level in the region rose from USD 141 to USD 3,689 during the period. The average FD value of 0.109 depicts an underdeveloped financial sector in the region, only experiencing slight improvement as reflected by the maximum value of 0.292. The mean of foreign direct investment and trade openness are 2.827 and 58.670% of GDP. Electricity production in the region averaged 2.951 billion kilowatt-hours (kWh) and rose to 32.3 billion kWh from 0.019 billion kWh between the period. This implies that there is insufficient electricity to power economic activities in the region and economic growth might be slowed by inadequate electricity production. Urban population in the regional countries grew at an average of 3.950% and peaked at 7.886% from a minimum of -1.065%. Throughout the period investigated, some variables recorded strong fluctuations, among them are: Economic growth, CO₂ emissions, trade openness, electricity production and natural resource rents.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	CO ₂	NR	EG	FD	FDI	EPD	URB	TON	INQ
CO ₂	1.000								
NR	0.0927*	1.000							
EG	0.4522*	0.2441*	1.000						
FD	0.5121*	0.1801*	0.7980*	1.000					
FDI	-0.0773	0.1852*	0.2458*	0.1360*	1.000				
EPD	0.9102*	0.0351	0.5343*	0.5588*	-0.0647	1.000			
URB	0.1123*	-0.0529	-0.2835*	-0.0378	-0.0852	0.0735	1.000		
TON	-0.2858*	0.3317*	0.3345*	0.1917*	0.3895*	-0.2091*	0.1754*	1.000	
INQ	-0.1807*	-0.1879*	0.3431*	0.3121*	0.0907	-0.0354	0.0839	0.2136*	1.000

Note: * show significance at 5%
Source: Author's computations (2025)

Table 2 shows the results of the pairwise correlation matrix among critical variables chosen for the study, providing invaluable understanding of the relationships between the pivotal variables and the factors influencing CO₂ emissions across the selected West African countries. Table 2 indicates that natural resource rents, economic growth, financial development, electricity production and urbanization are possible inducers of CO₂ emissions across the selected West African countries as positive correlation emerged between them and CO₂ emissions. Conversely, trade openness and institutional quality had inverse relationship with CO₂ emissions, indicating that strong institutional framework and an open economy which foster income growth and the adoption of eco-friendly production process and technology will reduce carbon emissions. Furthermore, the study observed that a positive correlation emerges between financial development and economic growth, foreign direct investment and economic growth, electricity production and economic growth, alluding to higher foreign capital inflow, developed financial system and energy catalysing economic growth. The correlation analysis was extended to other pivotal variables and the coefficients which are less than 0.85 underscores lack of correlation threat among the main variables included in the CO₂ model.

Table 3: Heterogeneity Test

Code	Mean	St. Dev.	Freq.	Test Statistics	
Benin	1.3170	0.3476	32	W0 = 8.1433 <i>df</i> (14, 462) Pr > F = 0.0000	
Burkina Faso	-0.2440	0.3163	32		
Cabo Verde	-0.6183	0.3083	32		
Cote d'Ivoire	-0.4347	0.1377	32		
Gambia	-0.9326	0.2544	32		
Ghana	-0.3820	0.4154	32		
Guinea	-0.0129	0.3458	30		W50 = 7.0843 <i>df</i> (14, 462) Pr > F = 0.0000
Guinea-Bissau	-0.1921	0.2576	31		
Mali	-0.0514	0.4447	32		
Mauritania	0.0927	0.2726	32		
Niger	0.0178	0.2387	32		
Nigeria	0.8129	0.2880	32		
Senegal	-0.0093	0.1538	32		
Sierra Leone	0.0036	0.4759	32		
Togo	0.6267	0.5550	32	W10 = 7.8381 <i>df</i> (14, 462) Pr > F = 0.0000	
Total	-2.234e-16	0.6428	477		

Source: As compiled by Author (2025)

Next, the study tested the notion that the slope coefficients are homogenous across the cross-sectional units in order to detect if the cross-sections have similar economic development movement, culture, or otherwise and control for its presence in order to avoid having estimation outcomes that are misleading. The results of the method introduced by [12] and [22] is presented in Table 3 and shows that the [22] computed W_0 statistics of 8.1433 and Brown and Forsythe (1974) W_{50} statistics of 7.0843 and W_{10} statistics of 7.8381 is statistically different from zero. The result of Table 3 proves that there is slope heterogeneity in the data, as the null hypothesis which assumes that the slopes are homogenous is rejected. Consequently, the study instils unbiasedness, consistency and trustworthiness in estimates by modeling parameter heterogeneity.

Table 4: Result of CSD Test

Test	Statistics	Prob.	Decision
Pesaran (2004) CD	1.412	0.1578	Independence

Source: As compiled by Author (2025)

The issue of cross-sectional dependence (CSD) has grave consequences in panel data analysis if not detected and addressed. The results obtained from estimating the panel model when CSD would be inconsistent and biased. To test if

the cross-sections are dependent, either through trade arrangement, globalization or other spatial spillovers, the Pesaran CD tests proposed by [17] was performed and the result presented in Table 4. In Table 4, the null hypothesis that which expresses that the cross-sections are independent is not rejected. In other words, the selected West African countries are independent of each other and shocks in one of the countries does not spillover to other countries in the panel.

Table 5: Panel Unit Root Result

Variables	Panel Unit Root				Remark
	Panel A: LLC		Panel B: IPS		
	Level	1 st Diff.	Level	1 st Diff.	
$lnco2_{i,t}$	1.0918	-10.6764***	4.4997	-12.3814***	I(1)
$nr_{i,t}$	-1.7200**	-	-2.9861***	-	I(0)
$lneg_{i,t}$	-0.4128	-6.0751***	3.8322	-8.6290***	I(1)
$fd_{i,t}$	0.3536	-12.1353***	0.1045	-14.8653***	I(1)
$fdi_{i,t}$	-2/5613***	-	-3.4377***	-	I(0)
$lnepd_{i,t}$	-1.0793	-7.1337***	2.9061	-8.4945***	I(1)
$urb_{i,t}$	-3.8975***	-	-5.4750***	-	I(0)
$ton_{i,t}$	-0.9467	-11.5415***	-1.5112*	-13.6389***	I(1)
$inq_{i,t}$	-1.9224**	-	-2.0038**	-	I(0)

Note: ***, ** & * is significance at 1, 5, and 10%

Source: As compiled by Author (2025)

After determining that there are no spatial spillovers or dependence of the cross-sections, the next phase in the analytical process involved an examination of the stationarity properties of the used in estimating the CO₂ model using the first-generation panel unit root tests. The study applied the panel unit root testing method credited to [23] and [17] to investigate this stationarity properties and ensure the estimation outcome is not spurious. The results of the tests are presented in Table 5. In Table 5, it can be seen that the null hypothesis that level values of the pivotal variables of natural resource rents, foreign direct investment, urbanization and institutional quality contain unit root is rejected, alluding to the variables being integrated of order zero I(0). In Table 5, the outcome of both the LLC and IPS tests indicate that CO₂ emissions, economic growth proxy, financial development, electricity production, and trade openness are not stationary at level, but stable at their first differences.

Table 6: Kao cointegration test result

	Statistic	Prob.
Modified DF	-1.4775*	0.0698
DF	-1.7105**	0.0436
ADF	-1.8936**	0.0291
Unadjusted modified DF	-3.5592***	0.0002
Unadjusted DF	-2.7486***	0.0030

Note: DF = Dickey-Fuller; ADF = Augmented DF; ***, ** & * is significance at 1, 5, and 10%

Source: As compiled by Author (2025)

Table 7: Westerlund cointegration result

	Statistic	Probability
Variance ratio	3.7876	0.0001

Note: ***, ** & * is significance at 1, 5, and 10%

Source: As compiled by Author (2025)

With slope heterogeneity, independence of the cross-sections and stationarity properties of the pivotal variables confirmed, the [18] and [37] approaches to illuminating cointegrating relationship were employed to detect co-movement among variables of the CO₂ model. The outcome of the Kao and Westerlund tests reported in Table 6 and 7 demonstrate an existence of stable cointegrating relationship among the pivotal variables, as the p-values of the ADF statistics and variance ratio statistics are low.

Table 8: PMG Result

Dependent Variable: $\ln\text{Co}2_{i,t}$				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistics	Prob.
Long Run				
$nr_{i,t}$	0.0357**	0.0168	2.1281	0.0344
$nr_{i,t} * inq_{i,t}$	0.0487***	0.0156	3.1156	0.0021
$inq_{i,t}$	-0.5201***	0.1817	-2.8622	0.0046
$lneg_{i,t}$	0.8138***	0.1876	4.3360	0.0000
$fd_{i,t}$	-3.8725***	0.8081	-4.7922	0.0000
$fdi_{i,t}$	0.0113	0.0069	1.6226	0.1061
$lnepd_{i,t}$	0.3999***	0.0963	4.1518	0.0000
$urb_{i,t}$	0.2200***	0.0506	4.3472	0.0000
$ton_{i,t}$	0.0061***	0.0012	4.8278	0.0000
Short Run				
ECM_{t-1}	-0.1724**	0.0664	-2.5948	0.0101
$d(nr_{i,t})$	0.0002	0.0195	0.0121	0.9903
$d(nr_{i,t} * inq_{i,t})$	-0.0127	0.0297	-0.4298	0.6677
$d(inq_{i,t})$	-0.1133	0.2530	-0.4479	0.6547
$d(lneg_{i,t})$	-0.2549	0.1838	-1.3869	0.1668
$d(fd_{i,t})$	0.3506	0.3838	0.9133	0.3620
$d(fdi_{i,t})$	0.0018	0.0056	0.3184	0.7505
$d(lnepd_{i,t})$	0.2318***	0.0706	3.2812	0.0012
$d(urb_{i,t})$	0.0040	0.0493	0.0815	0.9350
$d(ton_{i,t})$	0.0007	0.0011	0.7110	0.4778
c	-0.8973	0.3741	-2.3983	0.0173

Note: ***, ** & * is significance at 1, 5, and 10%
Source: As compiled by Author (2025)

Institutions have been identified as a domestic factor that can influence the relationship between natural resource rents and the quality of the environment. Institutions can affect the environment through policies such as removal of fuel subsidies which increase productions of fossil or hydrocarbons, carbon taxing, among others. Table 8 documents the outcome of the estimation specified to estimate the separate effect of natural resource rents and institutional quality and the interaction of natural resource rents and institutional quality proxy on the quality of environment in the West African countries, for the duration of the study, beginning from 1990 to 2022. The study employed the interaction of natural resource rents and institutional quality proxy ($NR_{it} * INQ_{it}$) to determine whether the environment quality impact of natural resource rents varies with the quality of institutions in the West African countries. The result of the Pooled Mean Group portrays that, natural resource rents significantly harm the environment of the West Africa countries. The estimated coefficient of 0.0357 suggest that the decision of the governments of West African to concentrate on rents or receipt from the sale of natural resource to finance their expenditure and not diversify their economies away from the extractive sector harms the environment in the long run. The finding is consistent with the discoveries of ([26]; [34]; and [38]). Table 8 reveals that institutional quality induces increase in the level of carbon emissions in the West Africa countries. These submissions are based on the individual coefficients of natural resource rents and institutional quality. The coefficient of the interactive term of natural resource rents and institution quality is positive and significant, suggesting that, for the fifteen (15) West Africa countries studied from 1990 to 2022, institutional quality in the form of regulatory control does not help in abating CO₂ emissions, but rather worsens the level of pollution. The implication of this result is that, the level of institutions in the West Africa countries has no potential in reducing the detrimental effect of natural resource rents on the environment.

v. Conclusion and Recommendation

Fossil fuels and minerals are vital natural resources that drive growth and expansion in developing countries. Since, revenue from natural resources helps fund government initiatives, such as, infrastructure development, public goods, social programs, and safety nets that improve living standards. This makes natural resource rent essential for developing

countries aspiring to join the league of developed nations, as it is a form of capital that can significantly facilitate economic growth. Although, natural resource exploitation is economically beneficial, it significantly contributes to rising greenhouse gas emissions, especially, carbon dioxide (CO₂) which drives environmental degradation. This study experiments this hypothesis by examining the impact of natural resource rents on environmental quality, using balanced dataset of fifteen (15) West African countries. The timeframe of the study started from 1990 and ran to 2022. The study is an improvement over previous contributions, by exploring both linear and nonlinear relationships between natural resource rents and environmental degradation. The analysis performed using the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) revealed that the level of CO₂ emissions increases as natural resource rents surges and the effect is significant. Further analysis revealed that regulatory quality not only fails to mitigate the negative environmental impact of natural resource rents but actually exacerbates the damage. To reduce the environmental impact, this study recommends that West African countries must go beyond institutional reform in name and focus on tangible enforcement mechanisms, technological innovation, and investment in renewable energy. Consequently, there is a need to scale up research and investment in alternate green or renewable energy sources such as hydropower, solar, wind, and geothermal, among others. Policymakers in the West African countries should implement regulatory policies designed to lower environmental degradation. Specifically, government of the West African countries should ensure that multinational firms operating within the extractive sector ecospace comply with the environmental regulations in each country and global best practices.

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